

Gallium(III) chloride as an efficient new catalyst for the production of Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines

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Abstract : Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines (DHPs) are synthesized in good to excellent yields from aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and ammonium acetate using gallium(III) chloride which acts as dehydrating agents and 5 mol% is enough for this protocol under solvent free conditions.

Keywords : Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines, gallium(III) chloride, aldehydes, 1,3-dicarbonyl compound, ammonium acetate, solvent-free.

Introduction

Originally in 1881¹ Hantzsch introduced a process for the production of 1,4-DHPs which were readily oxidized to produce pyridines and it was accepted as a good process for preparing a variety of substituted pyridines. Later on when their resemblance to NADH² (A) was reported, they started attracting attention of chemists to use these molecules as organo-reducers and a variety of functional groups have been successfully reduced³⁻⁶. In this process DHPs are oxidized to substitute pyridines. Also several other inorganic oxidants are used to achieve this target⁷⁻¹⁰. Further intensive researches followed after the disclosure of their interesting anti-hypertensive pharmacological activity¹¹ and systematic investigations have resulted into discovery of drugs like Nifedipine, Arandipine, Nicardipine, Nitrendipine and Amlodipine etc. which are drugs of choice in the market¹².

A

The DHPs are also known to possess activities like anti-thrombotics¹³, calcium channel blockers¹⁴, anti-inflammatory¹⁵, anti-tumor¹⁶, anti-tuberculosis¹⁷, analgesic¹⁸ and anti-convulsant agents¹⁹ etc. So undoubtedly DHP scaffold is in the category of privileged molecules¹². Therefore the production of these molecules in facile and in efficient manner is of current interest because as in the original procedure reported by Hantzsch there were several limitations¹. So to produce these molecules economically in high yields additives/catalysts continue to be reported. Mechanistically this reaction is established to proceed via Knoevenagel reaction followed by Michael reaction in all eventuality, two molecules of water are eliminated in this process²⁰. Keeping this in mind to achieve higher efficiency several catalysts and conditions are used and these include the use of microwaves²¹, ionic liquids²², Lewis acids like Yb(OTf)₃²³, CAN²⁴, K₇[PW₁₁CoO₄₀]²⁵, I₂²⁶ etc. After careful examination of these reports we conclude that there is a scope for further improvement in these production processes of DHPs as some of these procedures are very slow. Applications of GaCl₃ in organic synthesis are of current interest properties because of its dehydrating nature.

Results and discussion

We and others have been investigating the use of gallium and its salts in chemical transformations including selective protection of aldehydes²⁷, Biginelli²⁸,

Note

Reformatsky²⁹, Pechmann³⁰, Grignard³¹, Barbier reactions³², Strecker reaction³³, synthesis of 1,5-benzodiazepines³⁴ and synthesis of quinoxaline derivatives³⁵. Our own interest^{27,28,33,34,36} and these successful applications of gallium(III) halides as mild Lewis acids prompted us to explore its use in production of 1,4-DHPs which is the subject of present communication. When Ga^{III} halide, aldehyde, 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and ammonium acetate are heated at 60 °C under solvent free condition, DHPs obtained in excellent yields (Scheme 1).

The isolated yield was 79%. Like this way we used varying quantities of catalyst, viz. from 2 mol% to 10 mol% and optimized the catalyst quantity i.e. 5 mol% and obtained excellent results. Use of less amount of catalyst resulted in the decrease of product yield while increasing the amount of catalyst did not show any significant effect on the reaction rate as well as yields. To check the efficacy and applicability of this catalyst, we could successfully obtain a range of desired products in 82–95% yields

Scheme 1

The investigation of present work was initiated with 2 mol% GaCl₃, *para*-formaldehyde, ethylacetoacetate and ammonium acetate (1 : 2 : 2) by thoroughly mixing/stirring the contents at 60 °C under solvent free conditions.

(Table 1) and reaction completes within 12–19 min.

Conclusions :

In conclusion, the present protocol of employing GaCl₃ is mild, efficient and environment benign protocol for the

Table 1. Synthesis of substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines using 5 mol% GaCl₃ under solvent free condition

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Product ^a	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	H	OEt	4a	12	94
2	Me	OEt	4b	15	83
3	C ₆ H ₅	OEt	4c	17	89
4	3-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	OEt	4d	18	84
5	2-Furyl	OEt	4e	13	92
6	H	OMe	4f	14	95
7	Me	OMe	4g	19	89
8	C ₆ H ₅	OMe	4h	16	89
9	3-(NO ₂)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4i	19	86
10	4-(OMe)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4j	16	84
11	4-(Cl)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4k	18	92
12	2-Furyl	OMe	4l	15	95
13	4-(OH)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4m	18	85
14	2-(Cl)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4n	17	82
15	4-(Me)-C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4o	19	87

^aThe products were characterized by comparison of their melting points and spectral (IR, ¹H NMR) data with those of authentic samples.

^bIsolated yields after recrystallization.

synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines. Products are obtained in excellent yields in very short reaction time. Operation procedure is very simple and solvents free conditions are the other attractive features of this protocol which add green aspect to this procedure. There is no need to say that during work-up no hazardous/unsafe by-products were formed in this new method reported here.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Reagent-grade chemicals were purchased from commercial source and used without further purification. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyzer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Gemini 300 (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The chemical shifts of the protons are expressed in δ_{ppm} and the coupling constant (J) values in Hz. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel G (Merck).

General procedure for preparation of Hantzsch 1,4-dihydropyridines :

The mixture of aldehydes (10 mmol), a 1,3-dicarbonyl compound (20 mmol), ammonium acetate (20 mmol) and GaCl_3 (0.05 mmol) was stirred at 60 °C for time given in Table 1. After completion of reaction (Monitored via TLC), the mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (20 mL), and the organic layer was washed with saturated NaHCO_3 solution (3×15 mL) and then with brine. Organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure to give crude product which was purified by recrystallization from ethyl acetate-ether mixture.

Representative spectral data :

4a : m.p. 170–172 °C. IR (KBr) : 3352, 3107, 2987, 2898, 1693, 1654, 1507 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 1.30 (6H, t, J 3.48), 2.19 (2H, s), 3.26 (6H, s), 4.43 (4H, q, J 7.17), 8.70 (1H, s).

4b : m.p. 130–131 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 2963, 1697, 1642, 1492 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 0.96 (3H, d, J 6.45), 1.27 (6H, t, J 7.05), 2.26 (6H, s), 3.82 (1H, q, J 6.45), 4.12 (4H, m), 5.45 (1H, s); MS : (m/z) 267.14

(M^+), 265, 252, 236, 224, 220, 208, 196, 192, 178, 164, 150, 77, 43.

4c : m.p. 158–160 °C. IR (KBr) : 3341, 2981, 1687, 1650, 1488 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 1.19 (6H, t), 2.33 (6H, s), 4.04 (4H, m), 4.98 (1H, s), 5.52 (1H, s), 7.11–7.28 (5H, m); MS : (m/z) 329.16 (M^+), 327, 282, 254, 252, 236, 224, 210, 196, 180, 139.

4d : m.p. 159–161 °C. IR (KBr) : 3344, 3090, 2989, 2932, 1705, 1645, 1524, 1487 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 1.19 (6H, t), 2.36 (6H, s), 4.03 (4H, m), 5.09 (1H, s), 5.66 (1H, s), 7.34 (1H, m), 7.62 (1H, m), 7.98 (1H, m), 8.11 (1H, m); MS : (m/z) 374.14 (M^+), 355, 327, 299, 281, 252, 224, 196, 150, 127, 77, 43.

4e : m.p. 166–168 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 2982, 1699, 1650, 1488 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 1.23 (6H, t, J 7.11), 2.33 (6H, s), 4.07 (4H, m), 5.19 (1H, s), 5.69 (1H, s), 5.94 (1H, d, J 3.18), 6.20 (1H, dd, J 1.86), 7.21 (1H, d, J 1.62); MS : (m/z) 319.14 (M^+), 317, 290, 262, 246, 245, 218, 214, 174, 144, 115.

4f : m.p. 209–210 °C. IR (KBr) : 3345, 3107, 3005, 2949, 1697, 1646, 1505, 1431, 1383 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 2.85 (6H, s), 3.72 (2H, s), 3.93 (6H, s), 8.70 (1H, s); MS : (m/z) 225.10 (M^+), 224, 223, 210, 192, 165, 164, 132, 120, 104, 77, 43.

4g : m.p. 152–154 °C. IR (KBr) : 3341, 3266, 3108, 2949, 1680, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 0.94 (3H, d, J 6.30), 2.27 (6H, s), 3.71 (6H, s), 3.77 (1H, q, J 6.51), 5.52 (1H, s); MS : (m/z) 239.11 (M^+), 224, 208, 192, 178, 164, 149, 120, 43.

4h : m.p. 195–197 °C. IR (KBr) : 3343, 3081, 3026, 2950, 1699, 1649 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 2.34 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 5.00 (1H, s), 5.58 (1H, s), 7.12–7.25 (5H, m); MS : (m/z) 301.13 (M^+), 299, 267, 236, 224, 210, 192, 164, 77.

4i : m.p. 210–212 °C. IR (KBr) : 3349, 3005, 2953, 1704, 1650, 1528 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 2.37 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 5.10 (1H, s), 5.71 (1H, s), 7.25 (1H, t, J 7.89), 7.61 (1H, m), 7.98 (1H, m), 8.08 (1H, t, J 1.84); MS : (m/z) 346.11 (M^+), 344, 328, 327, 313, 297, 281, 224, 192, 152, 115, 43.

4l : m.p. 192–194 °C. IR (KBr) : 3344, 2951, 1698, 1651, 1492, 1434 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : 2.34 (6H, s), 3.70 (6H, s), 5.19 (1H, s), 5.70 (1H, s), 5.92 (1H, d,

J 3.21), 6.20 (1H, dd, *J* 1.90, 1.70), 7.21 (1H, d, *J* 1.66).

4m : m.p. 231–233 °C. IR (KBr) : 3329, 3001, 2953, 1681, 1650, 1611, 1589 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.33 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 4.70 (1H, s), 4.92 (1H, s), 5.57 (1H, s), 6.65 (2H, d, *J* 6.60), 7.10 (2H, d, *J* 6.66).

4o : m.p. 174–176 °C. IR (KBr) : 3314, 3105, 2942, 1697, 1655, 1495 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 2.27 (3H, s), 2.33 (6H, s), 3.64 (6H, s), 4.96 (1H, s), 5.62 (1H, s), 7.00 (2H, d, *J* 8.01), 7.14 (2H, d, *J* 8.07); MS : (*m/z*) 315.14 (M⁺), 313, 281, 250, 224, 192, 152, 115, 43.

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